

Original Research Article

Comparative Analysis of Different Activation Methods on Platelet Rich Plasma

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Abstract

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Platelet-rich plasma (PRP) emerged tremendously in all medical fields. Being easy to obtain, safe immunologically, and inexpensive made it attention-grabbing by researchers as well as health care givers. Platelet-rich plasma is considered as a source of several growth factors and cytokines which accelerate healing and help cell proliferation, differentiation, improved synthesis of extracellular matrix, and angiogenesis. These growth factors and cytokines are released by degranulation of platelets when activated internally or externally. We designed this study to compare different strategies of platelet-rich plasma activation by evaluating content and release of growth factors for further clinical trials to validate the clinical relevance of best method to help regeneration of liver in hepatic patients. This study was conducted on 21 participants (84 samples, 4 from each participant). Samples were divided into 4 groups: unactivated PRP (Group 1), activated PRP with calcium gluconate (group 2), activated PRP with thrombin (group 3), and activated PRP with thrombin plus calcium gluconate (group 4). Growth factors (PDGF-Ab & TGF-β) were measured in each sample using ELISA. Results obtained showed significantly higher GF (PDGF-AB & TGF-β) release from group 4 (where PRP activated with calcium gluconate plus thrombin) compared to the other groups. Group 3 (where PRP activated with thrombin) showed a higher significant increase in GF (PDGF-AB and TGF-β) release than in group 2 (where PRP activated with calcium gluconate) and group 1 (inactivated PRP group). Also, it has been found that the GF (PDGF-AB and TGF-β) released from group 2 were significantly higher compared to that released from group 1. It has been found that activated PRP using thrombin plus calcium gluconate release more growth factors than inactivated PRP. Our study also revealed that growth factors released from activated PRP using activators of thrombin plus calcium gluconate is better than using either as activator.

Keywords: Growth factors, PRP, Thrombin, Calcium gluconate

INTRODUCTION

Platelet Rich Plasma (PRP) has been a breakthrough in the stimulation and acceleration of healing for over 20 years, starting by tissue repair in dentistry and expanding to other clinical fields afterwards (Marx et al., 1998).

Nowadays, it represents a relatively new biotechnology that is part of growing interest for extensive research in tissue engineering and regenerative medicine (Niemeyer et al., 2010).

Platelet-rich plasma is autologous plasma with high platelet concentration. It is easy, cheap, safe, and minimally invasive source for autologous growth factors and cytokines (Cavallo et al., 2016). Several different growth factors and cytokines accelerate healing and help cell proliferation, differentiation, improved synthesis of extracellular matrix (ECM), and angiogenesis (neovascularization and formation of a new conjunctive tissue necessary for healing) (Marwah et al., 2014; Cervantes et al., 2018).

Growth factors (such as PDGF, bFGF, SDF 1 α), angiogenic factors (such as VEGF, angiogenin), necrotic factors (such as TNF α , TNF β), hemostatic factors (such as factor V, VWF, Fibrinogen), and other cytokines are the important contents of alpha granules. Alpha (α) granules, dense granules, and lysosomes are found in platelets with α granules - 80 granules per platelet - being most abundant (Blair and Flaumenhaft, 2009; Whiteheart, 2011).

The platelets can be activated by thrombin, calcium, collagen, and shear stress. Once activated, morphological changes of platelets and degranulation of their granules occur. Growth factors are released by degranulation either by fusion with the open canalicular system and extrusion of its contents through small channels in the cell membrane, or by exocytosis and releasing α granules content outside by fusing the granules with the cell membrane (Zandim et al., 2012).

Recently, platelets has been discovered to have a positive influence on the liver; as they accelerate liver regeneration (Murata et al., 2014; Takahashi et al., 2013) and have anti-fibrosis (Takahashi et al., 2013; Nowatari et al., 2014; Hesami et al., 2014) and anti-apoptotic activity (Hisakura et al., 2011). Platelets have a direct impact on hepatocytes, a supportive effect with liver sinusoidal endothelial cells, and a cooperative effect with Kupffer cells which accelerates liver regeneration (Takahashi et al., 2013).

Aim of the Work

To compare different strategies of PRP activation by evaluating content and release of growth factors for further clinical trials to validate the clinical relevance of best method to help regeneration of liver in hepatic patients.

SUBJECTS AND METHODS

This study was conducted on 21 participants. 10 ml blood was taken from each one of them divided into and one EDTA tube and 4 citrated tubes. The collected samples in EDTA group were tested for CBC of each participant. The collected samples in citrated tubes (84 samples, 4 from each participant) were divided into 4 groups. Volunteers

were recruited after a written consent was granted, with ethics committee approval of Theodor Bilharz Research Institute according to Helsinki Declaration.

Inclusion Criteria

Apparently healthy Volunteers with normal platelet count.

Exclusion Criteria

Systemic disorders, Smoking habit, Infection, Non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug use in the 5 days before blood donation, Platelets lower than $150 \times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$ or more than $400 \times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$

Platelet rich plasma preparation protocol

4 citrate tubes from each subject were centrifuged to get the PRP.

The Initial Centrifugation (Soft spin)

The citrate tubes are centrifuged at a force of $250 \text{ g} \times 10 \text{ min}$ to get PRP (Jun Araki et al; 2012). The plasma and buffy coat are transferred to another sterile tube (without anticoagulant).

The Second Centrifugation (Hard spin)

A second centrifugation is done at a higher speed of $2330 \text{ g} \times 10 \text{ min}$ (Jun Araki et al; 2012). The supernatant is discarded, pellet vortexed in 1 ml residual plasma and platelet count was adjusted to be 200-250 platelet.

Platelet Activation

Activation of PRP was performed by adding 10% of Cagluconate, 10% of autologous thrombin, 10% of a mixture of Cagluconate + thrombin. PRP without activation was used as control. PRP plus the added activator/s were incubated for 15-30 minutes at 37°C (Carola Cavallo et al., 2016). Then, samples were centrifuged at 800g for 10 minutes at 20°C , and the supernatants were collected (Huber et al., 2016).

PRP from each subject was divided into 4 groups according to the activator added:

Group I (Resting Group): no activator added

Group II (Calcium gluconate activated group)

Group III (Thrombin activated group)

Group IV (Thrombin + Calcium gluconate activated group)

Platelet Growth Factor Release Assay

➤ All tubes were centrifuged, Supernatant isolated and the assay was done the following day.

➤ PRP groups were evaluated for the release of Platelet Derived Growth Factor PDGF-AB and TGF-β1. Samples were evaluated using quantitative sandwich enzyme immunoassays following the manufacturer's instructions.

Statistical package and statistical analysis

The collected data will be revised, coded, tabulated and introduced to a PC using statistical package for social science (SPSS 15.0.1 for windows; SPSS Inc, Chicago, IL, 2001). Data is presented as a mean and standard deviation (\pm SD) for quantitative parametric data. Repeated anova analysis was done according to data. P-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant and P-value < 0.001 highly significant.

RESULTS

The present study was conducted on 21 healthy volunteers, their blood samples were analyzed, and a complete blood picture was done for each subject to record platelet number. Then samples were centrifuged and platelet concentrate outcome was documented. The study included 14 females and 7 male subjects, with sex ratio male to female 1:2, and their age is 35 ± 5 years old. The mean count of platelets for the subjects is 254 ± 50 . Platelets concentrate was adjusted to be 200-250/ml.

Results for PDGF-Ab

PDGF-AB level for resting group (group 1) was found to be $1,687.11\text{pg} \pm 29.55$, compared to $2,217.35\text{pg} \pm 32.49$ for PRP + calcium gluconate only, $2,469.57\text{pg} \pm 35.42$ for PRP + thrombin only, and $3,688.75\text{pg} \pm 82.35$ for PRP + (thrombin + calcium gluconate). Comparison of PDGF-Ab level results among the 3 groups of activated PRP (group 2 calcium gluconate, 3 thrombin, & 4 thrombin + calcium gluconate) with the resting group (inactivated PRP) showed that PRP activated with both calcium gluconate and thrombin gave the best outcome of growth factors released and the difference was statistically highly significant ($P < 0.001$). A statistically significant result of PDGF released from group 4 compared to group 3 ($P < 0.001$) and from group 4 compared to group 2 as well ($P < 0.001$). Also a statistically significant result of PDGF released from group 3 compared to group 2 ($P < 0.001$) (Table 1). PDGF-Ab level using calcium gluconate alone was 1.31 times PRP alone, using thrombin alone was 1.46 times PRP alone, and using calcium gluconate and thrombin was 2.2 times higher than that of PRP alone. Figure 1

Results for TGF- β

TGF- β level for PRP group was found to be $12.828\text{ng} \pm 0.971$, compared to $32.755\text{ng} \pm 0.480$ for PRP + calcium gluconate only, $48.821\text{ng} \pm 1.617$ for PRP + thrombin only, and $107.503\text{ng} \pm 1.202$ for PRP + (thrombin + calcium gluconate). Comparison of TGF- β level results among the 3 groups of activated PRP (group 2 calcium gluconate, 3 thrombin, and 4 thrombin + calcium gluconate) with the resting group (inactivated PRP) showed that PRP activated with both calcium gluconate and thrombin gave the best outcome of growth factors released and the difference was statistically highly significant ($P < 0.001$). A statistically significant result of TGF- β released from group 4 compared to group 3 ($P < 0.001$) and from group 4 compared to group 2 as well ($P < 0.001$). Also a statistically significant result of TGF- β released from group 3 compared to group 2 ($P < 0.001$). (Table 2)

TGF- β level using calcium gluconate alone was 2.6 times PRP alone, using thrombin alone was 3.8 times PRP alone, and using calcium gluconate and thrombin was 8.3 times higher than that of PRP alone. Figure 2, Table 1

DISCUSSION

Platelet-rich plasma has been used in various medical fields. It has recently emerged tremendously and attracted the attention of researchers as well as health care givers due to its abundance and ease of procurement, high immunological safety and cheap market price. Above all, it contains in its alpha granules numerous proteins (growth factors) that play an important role in many processes such as angiogenesis, coagulation, immune response and healing of damaged tissues.

Growth factors have been found to reflect an important feature of platelet rich plasma: multiple growth factor composition and nature-engineered concentration of each growth factor (Elham A. Masoudi et al., 2016). The goal of this study was to compare different strategies of PRP activation by evaluating content and release of growth factors for further clinical trials to validate the clinical relevance of best method to help regeneration of liver in hepatic patients.

In the current study we used citrated tubes in PRP preparation. Although tubes with different anticoagulants such as EDTA, ACD, or sodium citrate can be used, citrated tubes was found to be the best. RJFC do Amaral, et al. (2016) observed that platelet recovery was higher in the presence of sodium citrate compared to EDTA and ACD. The average of platelet recovery in sodium citrate was 81.21%, but it was 76.15% in EDTA; it was only 45.71% in ACD which is almost half of those when using

Figure 1. PDGF-Ab comparison between different activators of PRP
 Group 1: PRP (resting group) Group 2: PRP + Calcium gluconate only
 Group 3: PRP + Thrombin only Group 4: PRP + Thrombin + Calcium gluconate

Figure 2. TGF- β comparison between different activators of PRP
 Group 1: PRP (resting group) Group 2: PRP + Calcium gluconate only
 Group 3: PRP + Thrombin only Group 4: PRP + Thrombin + Calcium gluconate

Table 1. Comparison between mean ± SE of different activators of PRP with resting group

Groups	PDGF-AB(pg/ml)	TGF-β(ng/ml)
Group 1 (PRP)	1687.1 ± 29.6	12.828 ± 0.971
Group 2 (PRP+ Ca Gluconate)	2217.4 ± 32.5**	32.755 ± 0.480**
Group 3 (PRP+ Thrombin)	2469.6 ± 35.4**	48.821 ± 1.617**
Group 4 (PRP+ CaGlu+ Thrombin)	3688.8 ± 82.4**	107.503 ± 1.202**

Values represent mean ± SEM. **p< 0.001 as compared with Group 1 (PRP)

EDTA or sodium citrate (RJFC do Amaral et al., 2016).

In our study, we used the three wide spread methods for platelet stimulation; calcium gluconate, thrombin, and a mixture of both. The most commonly described human PRP activation methods use either calcium chloride/calcium gluconate or thrombin as the main platelet stimulants because they are very effective for eliciting growth factors release (Harrison S et al., 2011).

Regarding the use of calcium chloride or calcium gluconate as platelet activator, many studies showed no difference was found between growth factors concentrations in PRP supernatants activated with calcium gluconate or calcium chloride at the same concentration and dose, which may indicate that the PC could be activated by any of these substances (RF Silva et al., 2013). The process of activation by any of both (calcium chloride or calcium gluconate) is slower and more physiologic than that of externally provided thrombin, which bypasses all the activation steps and immediately initiates its receptor-driven activation process on the platelet. Calcium chloride/calcium gluconate, both, are widely described for clinical use, at a range of different concentrations (Sanchez M et al., 2007; Marx RE et al., 1998; Argüelles D et al., 2008; Gardner MJ et al., 2007). Calcium chloride/calcium gluconate is readily available as an inexpensive sterile solution (Diesen DL & Lawson JH, 2008). We used calcium gluconate in our study as it is cheaper and more available than calcium chloride.

The second widely used activator is thrombin. There are two types of thrombin; autologous and bovine. While autologous thrombin is significantly less effective, induces less platelet aggregation and expensive (Textor JA, Tablin F.; 2012), bovine thrombin is a fast, effective and available platelet activator which has been widely used for intraoperative PRP application in people since 1945 (Crean S et al.; 2010). That's why we preferred to use bovine thrombin over autologous thrombin.

In our study we evaluated growth factors, PDGF-AB and TGF- β 1, which are chosen among the most representative of PRP. Both are mainly derived from platelets and involved in every stage of tissue healing (Barrientos et al., 2008; Kaplan et al., 1979; Blakytyn et al., 2004) before and after platelets activation. PDGF is released from the platelets and plays important roles in relation to various cells. TGF- β , the other growth factor included in this study, is a multi-functional potential cytokine involved in the control of cell growth, stimulation of matrix production, and suppression of the immune system.

In this study, PDGF concentration in PRP increased significantly in response to platelet activation in all groups. This is agreed with the previous studies by Martineau et al., (2004), Tablin et al., (2008) and Textor & Tablin (2012). In this study, the PDGF-AB level in activated PRP using calcium gluconate/thrombin was 2.2 times higher than that in inactivated PRP. Similar results

observed by the study of Carrasco Luna et al. (2015) in which calcium/thrombin activated PRP was 1.9 times higher than in the inactivated PRP. Higher results observed by Weibrich et al. (2003) in which calcium/thrombin activated PRP was of 5 times higher than in the inactivated PRP.

Regarding group comparison, our study revealed that Calcium/thrombin produced significantly higher PDGF than that released with calcium or thrombin alone. Also, it has been found that thrombin alone produced significantly higher PDGF than that released with calcium alone. The same results were observed by Carola Cavallo et al. (2016) who reported that regarding PDGF-AB results, thrombin and CaCl₂/thrombin produced a significantly higher amount of PDGF compared to that produced by CaCl₂ alone. Similar results, with ours, regarding the increase of the growth factors contained in PRP after activation with calcium/thrombin, are obtained by Weibrich et al. (2003), Roussy et al. (2007) and Carrasco Luna et al. (2015).

The resulting TGF- β concentration in PRP in this study increased significantly in response to platelet activation in all groups. This was similar to other studies by Martineau et al. (2004), Tablin et al. (2008) and Textor & Tablin, (2012). In this study, the TGF- β level using calcium gluconate/thrombin was 8.3 times higher than that of inactivated PRP. The results of Carrasco Luna et al. (2015) has nearly the same quantitative measurement of ours, which were 8 times higher in the calcium/thrombin activated PRP than in the inactivated PRP.

In contrast to our results, Jeong Woo Lee et al. (2013) result was different regarding TGF- β which decreased after activation with thrombin/calcium chloride being 120.28 ± 1.74 ng/ml before activation and 118.7 ± 1.84 ng/ml after activation. Such differences in the quantitative analysis of growth factor (TGF- β) may be due to high-speed centrifugation used in their study. High speed centrifugation leads to low concentration of platelets and increased platelet membrane breakage which influence the activation of platelets by releasing growth factors before using thrombin/calcium chloride.

Regarding group comparison, as with PDGF-AB our study revealed that Calcium/thrombin produced significantly higher TGF β than that released with calcium or thrombin alone. Also, it has been found that thrombin alone produced significantly higher TGF β than that released with calcium alone. The same results were observed by Carola Cavallo et al. (2016) who reported that regarding TGF β results, thrombin and CaCl₂/thrombin produced a significantly higher amount of PDGF compared to that produced by CaCl₂ alone. Similar results, with ours, regarding the increase of the growth factors contained in PRP after activation with calcium/thrombin, are obtained by Weibrich et al. (2003), Roussy et al. (2007), and Carrasco Luna et al. (2015).

CONCLUSION

The released GF using calcium gluconate, and/or thrombin as activators for PRP is more than that released from PRP without activation (high significant difference). Released GF Using thrombin as an activator for PRP is more than that released from calcium gluconate activated PRP (high significant difference). Released GF Using thrombin plus calcium gluconate to activate PRP is more than that released from calcium gluconate or thrombin activated PRP (high significant difference).

RECOMMENDATIONS

We recommend using activated PRP with Thrombin and calcium clinically as results revealed best growth factors outcome, and more growth factors (other than PDGF-AB and TGF- β) to be tested after activation for confirmation of results. Inactivated and activated PRP, using the three methods of activation, to be used for clinical trials on hepatic patients with the same stage and with different stages of the disease to assess the clinical relevance of our results and to observe liver regeneration outcomes. Clinical trials to be done on a wide range of patients for more efficient statistical analysis of the results.

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